

THE PLACE AND ROLE OF INNOVATIONS AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF HUMAN RESOURCES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8016200>

Abstract. The article shows the high level of development of innovations today, the fact that we cannot imagine our lives without them, their rational use and proper direction can lead to positive results in any field. Including in the management of human resources, it is shown how important innovations and innovative technologies are in the management of human resources today.

Key words: Innovative development, human resources, project personnel management, positive and negative impact of innovations on human resources, project management, digitization.

"Human resources" as a socio-economic category reflects the most important laws, i.e. the processes of their reproduction, development, distribution and use, together with the formation of the labor force and the social relations that arise during the future labor activity. The term "human resources" was first used in science and management practice in the USA and Great Britain since 1970, and then in other countries with developed market economies. This is, first of all, by rethinking the role and place of a person in economic activity during the scientific and technical revolution and treating him not only as a "living" factor of production, but also as a personality with his own interests, motivation, psychology, personnel, entrepreneurship, etc. depends. Thus, the transition from the concept of a person as a passive, adaptable person to the conditions of external factors (XVIII/XIX centuries) to understanding him as a creator of his life, including his work career, is clearly visible. The recognition of the concept of "human resources" in our country as a concept that determines the level of development of the society (present and future) occurred due to the following circumstances. In recent years, the social and labor relations in the country have been transformed, the nature of the relations and even the ideology of the participants of the labor process has changed. Value orientations related to the mass of labor activity, equality of opportunities, and distribution based on labor contribution were replaced by entrepreneurship, personal competition, social status, and distribution of material capital. However, labor is still one of the most important factors of

production. Both the efficiency of the economic entity and the development of the society as a whole depend on the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of human resources, the efficiency of their use.

The presence of preschool age population in human resources is based on the following factors. Every person who comes into the world already has certain psychophysiological data, character, reaction, abilities for certain types of activities that form opportunities for further professional development, which are more clearly crystallized during preschool education and usually allow to go better in this process, during education, career choice. combined with the acquisition of certain skills. This contingent of citizens is also the owner of the experience of previous generations, the basis of the future economic well-being and security of any society. It is at the initial stage of the formation of a person that the state, its institutions, parents, and educators of preschool educational institutions require great attention to the issues of physical, intellectual, spiritual development, career guidance, and patriotic education. It justifies itself by investing financial resources, material resources, including funds in order to realize the tasks that must be performed in life, by reducing costs (public and individual) to find a suitable profession, a job that matches personal abilities, young people "jump" from one vocational educational institution to another. excludes "walking" and ultimately leads to the operation of enterprises with high economic efficiency. In this direction, on December 16, 2019, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev signed the law "On preschool education and upbringing". The main directions of the state policy in the field of education and training, as well as state guarantees for pre-school education and training were determined. On February 8, 2020, the Ministry of Neighborhood and Family Support was established by Decree No. PF-5938 "On measures to bring the system of work with family and women to a new level". It represents the part that is able to produce material goods and services due to their physiological and abilities. layer is included. In other words, labor resources are real and potential workers and are the most important component of the structure of human resources. At the same time, the difference between the general population and those who currently cannot participate in social production due to objective reasons determines the size of labor resources. To work in any field of activity, a person needs a certain spiritual (intellectual) and physical development. The directions of this development are determined, on the one hand, by economic, and on the other hand, by moral restrictions, that is, by the interest and opportunities of the

society to preserve and strengthen the health of its citizens as one of the important values of its society.

It is not for nothing that 2023 has been declared the year of "Attention to people and quality education". Today, the educational activities of universities are further improved, and the quality of our people's desire for knowledge, which has been formed over the centuries, is being demonstrated once again. For our young people to live a healthy and beautiful life, to have a permanent job in their profession, to take responsibility, not to allow them to belittle their human dignity, in short, they strive for perfection and see education as the most important prerequisite in this process.

Currently, the lowest age limit for working capacity is 16 years, and it is set up to 60 for men and 55 for women. But there are exceptions to this rule. For some types of professional activities associated with high psychophysiological stress on the human body, the pension plan is significantly lower - it differs by 5-10 or even more years. There is a system of "Preferential old-age pensions". This applies to production with unfavorable, difficult working conditions (for example, coal mining, metal smelting, etc.), as well as professions where the opportunity to maintain the desired "form of work" for years (for example, in ballet) is lost. According to the international classification, the labor force in Uzbekistan is divided into economically active and inactive population groups. Such a distribution makes it possible to manage the labor force at the national and regional level on the basis of global standards, while facilitating international comparison. According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1011 of December 22, 2017, the methodology of developing the balance of labor resources, employment and employment of the population, as well as the calculation of the unemployed population in need of employment was approved.

Today, it is difficult to find an area where innovation and innovative technologies have not reached. They are increasingly becoming an integral part of our lives. It should be noted that the main goal of creating innovations is to ease the problems faced by mankind. But their development and improvement from day to day has a significant impact on a number of factors such as labor force and human resources. As they say, there is a standard for everything, no matter how much the benefit is from them, it is appropriate to set a standard. Innovations are created by mankind, and they cannot fully replace their creators.

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